

Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment

skills

Erasmus+

HORVÁTH, László

Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment

Authors:

Dr. HORVÁTH, László – ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Institute of Education

The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

ISBN: 978-963-489-216-8

Publisher:

ELTE Eötvös Loránd University Department of Erasmus+ and International Programmes

2020

Recommended citation:

Horváth, L. (2020). *Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment*. Budapest: ELTE Eötvös Loránd University Department of Erasmus+ and International Programmes.

INTRODUCTION

The Quality and Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment is created during the Teach with Erasmus+ project (Project No.: 2018-1-HU01-KA203-047818). The aim of this document is to provide tools, templates, ideas to a) administration and management (e.g. vice-rectors or vice-deans for internationalisation, leaders and staff members of international offices etc.) and b) individual academics to foster institutional quality culture regarding teaching mobility and enhance the teaching mobility experience for instructors.

The Teach with Erasmus+ project (TWE+), as a logical continuation and extension of the staffmobility.eu website of the IMOTION project aims to create an online ‘Marketplace’ for teaching staff in order to **facilitate, encourage, and promote teachers’ mobility across Europe**. The project aims to enable greater access to teaching mobility and to compile innovative teaching methodologies and pedagogical tools all over Europe. This would be an unprecedented and crucial innovation for the European Higher Education Area, which would address some of the most pressing concerns and obstacles to academic mobility in the EU.

In order to help to fulfil this aim, the project has the objective to identify and define quality teaching mobility. This particular Intellectual Output (IO1) consists of exploratory research on quality aspects of teaching mobility that is followed by the development of the actual “**Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment**” (QITTMA) and is one of the four main pillars of the TWE+ project. In the premises of this research, an exploratory survey on elements connected to teaching mobility needs to be undertaken. This research will feed into the development of the actual tool.

The document is compiled, edited and created by Dr. László Horváth (ELTE Eötvös Loránd University) with the contribution of Luca Alexa Erdei (ELTE Eötvös Loránd University) building upon the results of the research conducted in the project. The sources of professional materials are indicated after each tools. The images used in this document are from pixabay.com.

The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

INSTITUTIONAL TOOLS TO FACILITATE A QUALITY CULTURE REGARDING TEACHING MOBILITY

The following section contains several tools for management or staff members of International Offices. The aim of these tools to facilitate a quality culture in the organization that could support activities related to teaching mobilities. The tools are strategic in view and many to be used by embedding into existing practices (e.g. quality assurance questionnaires, service evaluation forms and interviews etc.). It is our intention to provide evidence-based suggestions and topics to consider for institutions to be able to use these elements and tailor them to their individual needs.

The tools and suggestions are based on the international research project conducted in the Teach with Erasmus+ project.

The Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment contains the following items regarding institutional level:

- Guide points for strategic support of internationalisation
- Teaching Mobility Motivation and Hindering Factors Inventory
- Teaching Mobility Results Inventory
- Review of internal communication

Guide points for strategic support of internationalisation

Strategic planning is not new to higher education institutions. To aid universities in their strategic planning processes, the European Commission and the OECD developed the HEInnovate self-assessment tool (<https://heinnovate.eu/en>) that aims to explore the entrepreneurial and innovative potential of higher education institutions. HEInnovate covers eight areas:

- Leadership and Governance
- Organisational Capacity: Funding, People and Incentives
- Entrepreneurial Teaching and Learning
- Preparing and Supporting Entrepreneurs
- Digital Transformation and Capability
- Knowledge Exchange and Collaboration
- The Internationalised Institution
- Measuring Impact

It is not surprising, that internationalisation plays an important role in this tool. The TWE+ research on the quality of teaching mobility used the statements from the HEInnovate tool regarding strategic aspects of internationalisation with the following items.

Guide points for strategic support of internationalisation:

1. Internationalisation is an integral part of the HEI's entrepreneurial agenda.
2. The HEI explicitly supports the international mobility of its staff and students.
3. The HEI seeks and attracts international and entrepreneurial staff.
4. International perspectives are reflected in the HEI's approach to teaching.
5. The international dimension is reflected in the HEI's approach to research.

How to use this tool?

- 1) You can use the above-mentioned five items to assess the extent of how internationalisation is embedded in your organisation's strategy (either as a guide for document analysis or prompts to an interview or items for a questionnaire).
- 2) You can use the HEInnovate self-assessment tool to initiate a full institutional self-assessment with all eight areas, using the online system of HEInnovate that provides you with comparison and group-level statistics as well.
- 3) The HEInnovate tool offers a workshop guide for facilitators on how to conduct sense-making workshop to help administrators gather information or align viewpoints regarding strategic aspects of the university. You can focus on all areas of the HEInnovate or just on internationalisation. The training manual is available for download here:
https://heinnovate.eu/system/files_force/heinnovate_training_manual.pdf?download=1

What the research says?

- In our research on quality and impact of teaching mobility we have found that perceived strategic focus on internationalisation play an important role in issues regarding teaching mobility.

- For example, institutions where respondents reported lower levels of strategic focus on internationalisation also reported higher levels on factors that hinder academics

participation in teaching mobility programmes. And on the contrary: where perceived strategic focus on internationalisation was higher it corresponded to lower perceptions of hindering factors.

- Also, it was concluded in our research that if organisations show positive attitude towards internationalisation (strategic focus, organisational support) it correlates to higher satisfaction and higher return intent for academics regarding their teaching mobility experience.

Teaching Mobility Motivation and Hindering Factors Inventory

The following list of items are an extract from the TWE+ research on the quality of teaching mobility. Based on extensive semi-structured interview from all around Europe and an international workshop, the following possible motivational and hindering factors were identified for participating in teaching mobilities. The items are clustered as a results of an exploratory factor analysis.

How to use this tool?

- 1) You can add these (or a selection of these) items to your own institutional questionnaire if you want to assess possible hindering or motivational factors regarding participation in teaching mobilities and plan actions according to the results.
- 2) You can use these items to structure and facilitate interviews or focus group discussions to gather information regarding academics motivation or perceived hinderances regarding participation in teaching mobility.
- 3) You can use these items to develop a professional development plan or other strategies to foster teaching mobility in your institution.
- 4) As an individual academic, you can use these items to structure your self-reflection or the planning of your professional development.

Teaching Mobility Hindering Factors Inventory

Lack of time and financial support	It is hard for me to plan this opportunity ahead.
	I have no time to participate in such activities.
	I can't solve my substitution at my workplace.
	I fear that the budget available in the programme wouldn't be enough.
	It comes with great inconvenience to organise and execute it.
	I can't finance my mobility in advance.
	I find administrative tasks regarding teaching mobility quite complicated.
	I don't want to leave my family even for a short period of time.
Lack of connections and reputation or communication issues	I don't have adequate contacts.
	It is hard to communicate with the host institution.
	I'm not a well-known academic in my field yet for host institutions to accept me.
	I don't have enough information regarding the opportunity.
	It would be hard for me to organize the required number of lessons.
Lack of competence and motivation	I'm not confident enough in my foreign language skills.
	I'm not confident enough in my pedagogical competences.
	I prefer someone else to seize the opportunity

	There are no opportunities in those languages that I speak.
	I don't have any motivation to participate.
Intercultural difficulties	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different needs and expectations of students.
	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different national/educational systems.
	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different research / disciplinary culture of the host institution.
No benefits	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different needs and expectations of students.
	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different national/educational systems.
	Teaching mobility is hard to implement due to the different research / disciplinary culture of the host institution.

Teaching Mobility Motivational Factors Inventory

Learning (languages, pedagogical methods)	To improve my competencies in teaching in a foreign language
	To try out myself in a foreign language environment
	To improve my foreign language skills
	To improve my general pedagogical competencies
Getting to know new places, cultures	I wanted to learn about the culture of the host country
	I wanted to learn about the higher education system of the host country
	I wanted to learn about the educational practices at the host institution
	I love to travel
Research opportunities	Possible research opportunities
	Possible opportunities for joint-projects
	I wanted to learn about the research projects of the host institution
Expectation, urge	Encouragement from the leadership
	Expectation from my organisation
	Recommendation from a colleague
	A previous teaching mobility experience

What the research says?

- The data tells us, that academics who have participated in teaching mobility were mainly motivated by their **inner curiosity to learn new educational practices** (84,4% felt that this was very important motivation for them), and to **learn about the research projects of the host institution** (81,3% found it very important), but also the **possibilities for joint-projects** played an important role in their decision (81,9% found it very important). It is evident that teaching mobility is influenced by other factors than educational purposes.

- On the other side, it seems that **expectations or encouragement** from the organisation or the leadership is simply not that important (55,6% and 53,1% stated that these factors were not important in their decision), also which is quite contradictory to our expectations, **recommendations from colleagues** proved to be a weak factor as well (45,6% stated that this was not important). From these results, it seems that the decision to go on teaching mobility is influenced by internal rather than external factors.
- The most important hindering factors reported by participants are considering the administrative and organization tasks regarding mobility. 30,55% of respondents stated that it is a **great inconvenience to organise and realise** teaching mobility, while 28,32%

fear that the budget won't be enough to cover their expenses, 26,4% has issues with **solving their substitution at their home university** for the duration of the mobility. Nearly a quarter of the respondents simply **can't find the time to participate** in such activities.

- It seems that lack of **pedagogical competences, foreign language skills and a lack of opportunities** in the languages known by the respondents are less of an issue (more than 80% of respondents stated that these are not an issue for them).

Teaching Mobility Results Inventory

The following list of items are an extract from the TWE+ research on the quality of teaching mobility. Based on extensive semi-structured interview from all around Europe and an international workshop, the following possible results were identified as benefits of teaching mobilities. The items are clustered as educational, research, professional development and organisational results.

How to use this tool?

- 1) You can add the following (or a selection of) items to your own quality assurance questionnaire or feedback form where respondents could either select the items that they feel have happened related to their mobility experience, or they can rate this on a scale of your choice.
- 2) You can use these items to structure and facilitate a meeting or feedback session for knowledge and experience sharing regarding teaching mobility experience.
- 3) You can incorporate these items in an institutional strategy as preferred set of goals regarding the outcomes of teaching mobility.
- 4) As an individual academic, you can use these items to structure your self-reflection or the planning of your professional development.

Teaching Mobility Results Inventory:

Educational results	I understand our international students better (not language-wise)
	I can better adapt to the different needs and expectations of students
	I have learnt new teaching methods
	I have become more conscious regarding my approach to teaching
	My pedagogical competences have improved
	Students now have the opportunity to participate in joint professional practices and fieldwork with the host institution
	We have developed new course contents and materials with the colleagues of the host institution
	We have developed new courses with the colleagues of the host institution
Research results	Opportunity to present my research results
	Opportunity to get to know research projects at the host institution
	Access to the infrastructure of the host institution (library, databases etc.)
	Receive feedback on my topic
	I was able to submit an article to an international scholarly journal
	I was able to write a joint publication with the colleagues of the host institution
	I was able to launch a joint research project with the host institution
	I have invited a colleague from the host institution as a keynote speaker for our conference
I was invited to be a keynote speaker in a conference organized by the host institution	
Professional development results	My professional network has expanded
	I was invited as a guest lecturer to the host institution
	The content that I was teaching became a part of the regular curriculum of the host institution and I regularly teach that course there
	My mobility experience had a positive impact on my career development
	I've got to know the culture, educational system and the operation of higher education institutions of a foreign country
	I've got to know the work-culture of another organisation
My stress-management skills have improved	

	I became more flexible
	My interpersonal skills have improved
	My language skills have improved
	My cooperation skills have improved
	My intercultural skills have improved
	My professional overview has been expanded
	I became more motivated, the mobility experience inspired me
Organisational results	My institution became known at the host institution
	We have introduced a new course / module in our institution thanks to my mobility experiences
	We have introduced a new joint degree programme with the host institution
	The international reputation of my home institution increased in the eyes of our students
	My mobility contributed to the implementation of the internationalization strategy of our institution
	Thanks to my mobility, the number of student mobilities between the two institutions has increased
	My trust has grown regarding accepting ECTS from external institutions

What the research says?

- In our research we have found that academics reported overall higher intensity of **results on all areas** when they had a **previous teaching mobility experience** (they were a more conscious mobility teachers), when they have received **useful feedback from students** at the host university and when they had additional **motivation regarding their research** activities.
- Besides these three common factors, academics reported higher outcomes regarding **education**, when they had a **motivation to learn** (e.g. the language of the host country, new pedagogical methods) and when they felt that teaching mobility is an **expectation** from their institution/leadership.
- Besides the common factors, academics reported higher intensity of results regarding **research** areas when there were an **organizational strategy** for internationalisation at place at their home university.
- Besides the common factors, results regarding the **professional development** of academics were higher when it was coupled with a **motivation to learn** (new languages, pedagogical methods), a **motivation to get to know new places and cultures**, when teaching mobility was perceived as an **expectation** from the institution/leadership but these results were also **hindered if academics felt that they lack competence and motivation**.

- Finally, besides the common factors, **organisational outcomes** were mainly influenced by academics feeling of **self-efficacy**, the considering of teaching mobility as **expectation**, but these results could be hindered by the feeling of lack of competences and motivation.

Review of internal communication

Our research shows that internal communication regarding teaching mobility is an important but complex aspect. Respondents in our survey reported e-mails as the most frequent channel that they get information regarding teaching mobility. If an institution decides to enhance the visibility of teaching mobility programmes there are lots of things to do.

Try to develop a communication strategy or campaigns to promote teaching mobility at your institutions. Here, we share a few innovative examples and good practices that you can adapt to your own situation:

- use short video-spots where you interview previous participants of teaching mobility to share their experiences
- have several volunteering teaching mobility participants to write a blog regarding their experiences during a teaching mobility and promote their posts through appropriate channels
- organise informal meetings (learning cafés, dissemination seminars etc.) where recent teaching mobility participants can share their experiences with an interested audience using participatory methods (instead of a lecture-style presentation)
- create infographic regarding the basic information that academics need to know about applying to teaching mobility

What the research says?

- In general, it is considered a good strategy to raise potential participants' awareness regarding teaching mobility opportunities, but it can have an adverse effect as well. In our research we saw a tendency when formal communication regarding teaching mobility was more prevalent in an institution a higher rate of fear regarding one's lack of competences and motivation arose.

Further sources to consult:

- Case studies of good practices in higher education institutions internal communication:
<http://www.theknowledgepartnership.com/media/1065/helix-case-studies1.pdf>

TOOLS FOR ACADEMICS TO ENHANCE THEIR TEACHING MOBILITY EXPERIENCE

The following section contains several tools for individual academics. The aim of these tools to enhance academics teaching mobility experience. The tools are suggestions for different areas that could be important in a teaching mobility, therefore we encourage to use them as a stepping point and customize them to your need. It is our intention to provide evidence-based suggestions and topics to consider for academics to be able to use these elements and tailor them to their individual needs.

The tools and suggestions are based on the international research project conducted in the Teach with Erasmus+ project.

The Quality & Impact Tool for Teaching Mobility Assessment contains the following items regarding academics' level:

- Course Portfolio
- Getting to know your students – Intercultural Understanding Inventory
- Planning your course – constructive alignment
- Teaching international students – innovative pedagogical methods
- Getting useful feedback from students – student evaluation of teaching

Course Portfolio

What is the purpose of a course portfolio?

Many creative and effective teaching strategies are forgotten or misplaced between semesters, only to be re-learned in subsequent semesters or lost forever. In several faculties, no formal mechanism is in place to pass course-specific teaching information from instructor to instructor. A solution to this problem is the course portfolio, a resource exchange of course-specific teaching information.

A course portfolio can also be understood as a coherent narrative or investigation of a specific course that is documented, and reflected upon, as it is being taught. Its purpose is to capture and document all of the insights that you have over the course of the semester that you can then use to enhance and enrich the course the next time you teach it.

These insights may relate to a course that you have taught many times and now seek to ‘refresh’, to a course that you are teaching the first time, or to elements of a course that you are now approaching in a new way. Course portfolios also serve to guide reflection on your teaching and learning practices, and to act as a vehicle to give structure to the process of developing or enhancing your courses. A finished portfolio will include both supporting documents that are created along the way, as well as an analysis of those documents once the course has been completed.

Why should instructors make a course portfolio?

Course portfolios prevent the loss of effective teaching techniques, thus providing the means for all instructors to continually improve existing curriculum. Course portfolios will enable most instructors get a head start, specifically those who are new to campus, those who are teaching for the first time, or those who receive late assignments and have little time to prepare. By performing all of these functions, course portfolios will complement existing workshops and resources. Finally, course portfolios are useful for instructors who plan to continue teaching. Course portfolios can be revised into teaching portfolios, which may be useful documentation to present at job interviews and list on a vitae.

Of course, none of these benefits are possible if no one bothers to put anything in the course portfolio! Some instructors may be hesitant to put together their own course portfolio because they are concerned about the time involved. However, many of the items that could be in your course portfolio are things that you already have. You just need to collect and organize them. The portfolios may not be complete, but every bit will help the next instructor or help you the next time you teach the course. Additionally, by having course portfolios from previous semesters, instructors can spend more time developing new material for their course to supplement and enhance the previously collected material.

Creating a course portfolio can have significant benefits for both faculty and their students. For faculty, benefits include:

- A repository of teaching strategies and techniques to draw on when building new courses or enhancing existing ones
- An opportunity for individual reflection on teaching and learning practices
- An ongoing record of developing practice

- A method for systematically collecting feedback and insights on courses and teaching

How will course portfolios help international students?

International students will benefit by more effective teachers earlier in the semester. By using course portfolios from previous semesters, new instructors can provide students with some immediate materials that worked well in the past, thus enabling students to learn more easily while the instructor can take more time to prepare effective materials for future sessions. Instructors will have more time to focus on teaching techniques, curriculum revisions, or learning styles of the students. Also, the cumulative nature of the course portfolio will help the instructor avoid previous mistakes and identify common difficulties that students experience.

The benefits for students can be summarized as follows:

- More effective teaching strategies employed by instructors
- A systematised way to benefit from feedback from previous cohorts
- The opportunity to contribute to the future development other course

Content of a course portfolio

The portfolio begins with checklists, which are intended to help remind you to place material into the portfolio as well as to let others know what information you have placed in the course portfolio. Because you will probably be adding to your portfolio several times during the semester, we have separate checklists for various times: before the first day, after your first day, during the semester, and after the last day.

Before your first day, you should read what others have placed into the course portfolio and gather other appropriate handouts. If changes to the handouts are necessary for the new semester, make them before including them in the portfolio. During the semester, you may have additional handouts and assignments for the students. You also may have corrections, observations, homework solutions, and grading criteria to document. To save time, add materials to the portfolio as they become available to you, rather than hunting them all down at the end of the semester. The end of the semester is a time for instructors and students to reflect upon what worked, what didn't work, and what needs to be improved for next time. Be sure to note any corrections or changes.

The following checklist contains a non-exhaustive list and an additional short description of the core elements of the portfolio.

Course Portfolio Checklist

Type of document	Description	Done (Y/N)
BEFORE THE FIRST DAY		
1. Skim the portfolio from past semesters		
2. Syllabus and related information	In general, a syllabus covers topics such as the learning outcomes, course design, teaching/learning goals and	

	<p>objectives, learning activities, teaching methods, and assessment strategies. Specifically, a syllabus contains an outline and schedule of topics taught in the course. Also, the syllabus communicates to students what the course is about, why it is taught, where it is going, and what will be required of the students to pass the course. Last semester's syllabus is a good place to start when creating a new syllabus. While teaching the course, keep track of topics that took more or less time to cover than you predicted. Include suggestions about reorganizing or combining topics, or whatever ideas you have that would make the class run more smoothly.</p>	
2.1 Course description	<p>https://classroom.synonym.com/difference-between-course-description-syllabus-3962.html</p>	
2.2 Description of Learning Outcomes	<p>The Course Learning Outcomes are the statements that specify what the students should be able to know, perform, and demonstrate throughout a course (e.g., knowledge, skills, and attitudes). They need to be closely related to the learning outcomes of the program, and connected to the overall department and university goals and the characteristics of the graduates. Each course in the program aims to achieve a number of specific Program Learning Outcomes (PLOs). They help the teacher to select the content, determine the teaching methods and activities, and assess achievement. They also help the students to understand what is required of them to successfully complete the course. Through the course alignment matrix you have identified how each course contributes to achieving the PLOs. While each PLO describes in general terms what the student has to achieve upon graduation, at the course level these learning outcomes have to be more specific and describe what level of the learning outcomes the student needs to achieve at the end of the course. More than one course can contribute to achieving a program-learning outcome. The department has to then identify and clarify the different levels of achievement of the learning outcomes. In other words, there should be agreement about how the courses help students to systematically progress towards the learning outcomes and to ensure that by the end of the program there are no gaps or weaknesses in the students' experience. The literature provides a variety of ways to identify levels of progression. Depending on the type of learning outcome (subject knowledge, skill, or attitude), there are different ways of describing the level of how a certain course addresses a specific learning outcome, such as basic, intermediate, or advanced. Whatever scale is being used, the department has to agree on criteria for each identified level and indicators for</p>	

	<p>assessment. The course portfolio elaborates and gives details about the particular level of progression of the learning outcome for each course. In order to write effective learning outcomes, you need to ask the following questions (which can also serve as an assessment checklist).</p>																			
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="272 517 1058 562">Learning Outcome</th> <th data-bbox="1058 517 1158 562">Yes</th> <th data-bbox="1158 517 1257 562">No</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="272 562 1058 658"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome help to fulfill the specific learning outcomes of the program as specified by the department? </td> <td data-bbox="1058 562 1158 658"></td> <td data-bbox="1158 562 1257 658"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="272 658 1058 779"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome reflect the expected knowledge, skills, or attitudes that the department has set for the students' level? </td> <td data-bbox="1058 658 1158 779"></td> <td data-bbox="1158 658 1257 779"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="272 779 1058 875"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome detail what the students need to know, perform or demonstrate? </td> <td data-bbox="1058 779 1158 875"></td> <td data-bbox="1158 779 1257 875"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="272 875 1058 996"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome easily translated into a measurable activity and/or assignment? </td> <td data-bbox="1058 875 1158 996"></td> <td data-bbox="1158 875 1257 996"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="272 996 1058 1093"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome supported by success criteria helps the students to demonstrate successful achievement practically? </td> <td data-bbox="1058 996 1158 1093"></td> <td data-bbox="1158 996 1257 1093"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Learning Outcome	Yes	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome help to fulfill the specific learning outcomes of the program as specified by the department? 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome reflect the expected knowledge, skills, or attitudes that the department has set for the students' level? 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome detail what the students need to know, perform or demonstrate? 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome easily translated into a measurable activity and/or assignment? 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome supported by success criteria helps the students to demonstrate successful achievement practically? 			
Learning Outcome	Yes	No																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome help to fulfill the specific learning outcomes of the program as specified by the department? 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome reflect the expected knowledge, skills, or attitudes that the department has set for the students' level? 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the learning outcome detail what the students need to know, perform or demonstrate? 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome easily translated into a measurable activity and/or assignment? 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learning outcome supported by success criteria helps the students to demonstrate successful achievement practically? 																				
<p>2.3 Teaching methods</p>	<p>The decision on what teaching methods to use for the course is dependent upon the nature of the course and its learning outcomes. In preparing for the course, you need to consider the best methods to apply in order to achieve the required learning outcome. The following table may help to align each learning outcome with the teaching methods that you believe would be best. You may choose more than one method for each learning outcome. The course portfolio should include such a table and some reflection on the effectiveness of the teaching methods and learning activities that you use.</p>																			

3. Teaching materials	This section should contain all the materials considered essential to teaching your course. Please keep the materials updated, especially if a new instructor will be teaching the course next semester, and place them in the portfolio. Of course, you may want to make a copy to keep for yourself!	
3.1 Textbooks and reading materials	Once the learning outcomes are set and prioritized, the selection of the content and its format becomes an easy task. Whether it is a textbook, collected material, or some other form of learning resource, it needs to help students to advance their knowledge at the level they are at; to sharpen the skills necessary to graduate from the program; and help them to think and develop become active and effective individuals in their respective departments and in the society at large. The course portfolio should include a list of suitable readings and materials and how to access them. In the reflection part of the portfolio, you should briefly discuss the quality of the readings and explain how they help students to achieve the learning outcomes.	
3.2 Lecture notes	Include paper or transparency copies of the lecture notes. Staple or paper-clip the pages for each lecture together and keep them organized chronologically.	
3.3 Additions and revisions	Include any other core teaching materials such as a bibliography of supplemental textbooks if one is not included within the course manual. If you used supplemental texts, please make sure that the chapters used from each text are noted.	
4. Support materials	This section should list all relevant ...	
4.1 Online learning opportunities		
4.2 Computer files, programs, documentation	Whether or not you have assignments that are to be done on a computer, you may have computer files, softwares or applications related to the course. This section might include programs, data files, source code, sample files, online documentation, the electronic version of your handouts, etc.. Include a link to a specific folder or website. Please also state where any written documentation for the software/application can be found.	
4.3 Departmental resources and shops		
5. Assignments and assessments	This section of the course portfolio covers the expected format for assignments, problems, laboratory experiments, handouts, problems, quizzes, and exams. Homework problem sources and page numbers should be provided if	

	<p>they are from a textbook. This section will give the next instructor an idea about the questions asked in exams and your old homework assignment problems can be used in future discussions.</p> <p>Corrections, suggestions for improvement, and specific grading criteria such as what factors will be included, how they will be weighted, and how they will be translated into grades should be included with the assignments. You may also include your grading criteria and partial credit policy. If you grade several assignments the same way, just indicate your grading scheme once. You may write corrections and suggestions directly on the old copy of the assignment.</p>	
5.1. Expected format for assignments	<p>Some instructors expect students to turn in their assignments in a particular format. For example, reports should be typed, lab write-ups should include an abstract, or computer printouts should be in a monospaced font. If you have any guidelines for the preparation of homework assignments, lab reports, or take-home exams, include those guidelines in this section. If you would like to pass along the reason why you preferred your formatting style (easiness to grade, better presentation, etc.), please do so. This information is often in a course syllabus.</p>	
5.2. Examples of assignments		
6. Reflections before the first day	<p>This section might be best thought of as “big picture” in which you provide the overall context for the course. A helpful way to think about what to include is to imagine that you are talking to the next instructor about planning the course. Background information about the types of students enrolled in the course is helpful. Is your course introductory or maybe an elective with students who bring a wide range of skills and experiences to the course? Include comments about unique aspects of the course that might prove challenging to students. For example, do students use computers in lab for the first time? You may also include details about where the course fits into the major program of study. If you are a TA, and are teaching the course for the first time, it is important that you talk with the professor to help you understand the course context. <i>Form 1</i> can help you in organizing your thoughts.</p>	
AFTER THE FIRST DAY		
1. Reflections after the first day	<p>We have provided you with <i>Form 2</i> that asks several questions about how you prepared for the first day of class. Your insight can help instructors who teach the course next</p>	

	time and remind you of what needs to be done in order to improve the course for future semesters. We recommend that you answer these questions soon after your first class day, while the answers are still fresh in your mind.	
DURING THE SEMESTER		
1. Teaching materials additions and revisions		
2. Support materials additions and revisions		
2.1 Homework problems	Note the details about where assignment problems originated. Sometimes the problems are assigned by number from a textbook. In this case, the assigned problems might already have been listed in the course schedule; if they are coming from different books, indicate their page, author, and if necessary the edition number of the book. Other assignments that you should include are computer exercises and problem sets that include the full description of the problem; these may already have been given to students in other handouts.	
2.2 Quizzes and exams	Whether to include quizzes and exams in the course portfolio is an instructor decision. Many instructors consider these items to be sensitive material to which students should not be allowed access. Include quizzes, bench exams, midterms, and final exams and provide their solution sets, only if appropriate.	
3. Samples of student work	Examples of student work are an important part of the course portfolio. Include good, average, and poor examples of assignments, exams, or lab reports. If applicable, include a list of previous student projects. Also include the grading guidelines. Putting student samples into your course portfolio will give the next instructor an idea of the variety of student work in the class. Student privacy is important. Any student work samples you choose to include in the portfolio must be anonymous—remove the student’s name and other identifying information.	
4. Reflections during the semester	Most ideas for improvement occur as the semester progresses. You may document your observations on <i>Form 3</i> . Ideally you should reflect upon every assignment or chapter in your course; use your own judgment on how often you will need to do this. For example, you may write down your personal reflections once a week or for every major section of the class. Also, incorporate student feedback into your reflections.	

5. Summary of relevant e-mails	If you receive a message that you think would help in future semesters, you may print it or summarize it.	
AFTER THE SEMESTER		
1. Teaching or course philosophy		
2. Teaching materials additions and revisions		
3. Support materials additions and revisions		
4. Assignments and list of student projects		
5. Analysis of student performance		
6. Student feedback and evaluations	The most valuable component of the course portfolio is the section that contains the constructive criticism of the instructors and students. Departments usually require students to complete a course evaluation form at the end of the semester. Students are an excellent source of feedback regarding improvements to the course. If you have access to their comments or a summary of their ratings, consider including them in the course portfolio. If you made your own custom evaluations about your class, you may also include them. Remember that you should NOT include any evaluations of the people teaching the course. Only course evaluations should be included in the portfolio.	
7. Reflections after the semester	The most important part of this portfolio may be your reflections at the end of the semester. You will have your best impression of the course soon after your last day of teaching. Here is the place where you can give your personal reflections and evaluation of the class. Any educational or motivational suggestions are encouraged. If you have any “I wish I had done that ...” or “If I teach this course again, I would do this and that differently” comments, this section is the right place to add your ideas. Passing on information such as the difficulty of problems in assignment sets and exams, motivation of students, strengths and weaknesses of students, and problems with lab equipment will be helpful to the next instructor. Please take the time to note on <i>Form 4</i> what worked, what didn't work, and most importantly, what needs to be improved for the future. Therefore conclusions and next steps to be taken are inevitable parts of this section.	

Form 1: Reflections Before the First Day

1. What prerequisite knowledge do students need to have (i.e., talents, skills, and prior courses)?
2. What are the typical students like who take the course (e.g., new students, different majors, etc.)?
3. What will students find unique or different about the course (e.g., first time using a specific method or equipment, etc.)?
4. Did you contact previous teachers or TAs? If so, who were they?

Form 2: Reflections After the First Day

1. Did you need to check out any keys (e.g., cabinet or audio/visual equipment)? If so, please give details.
2. What other things did you have to do to prepare for the first day?
3. What educational or motivational suggestions would you share with the next instructor?
4. What did you cover the first day (use back of form if necessary)? Please provide an outline if possible.

Form 3: Reflections After Specific Learning Activity

Complete a form for each activity that you believe will provide useful information for the next instructor.

Type of Activity: e.g. Lecture/ Discussion/ Group work/ Experiment/ Quiz/ Exam/ Other:

1. What was the title or name of the activity?
2. Describe the activity and list the learning goals/objectives.
3. How do you know the students learned what you had hoped they learned? How do you assess student performance (i.e., feedback from students, observations, written assignments, etc.)?
4. What were common mistakes and/or what caused students trouble?
5. What educational improvements would you recommend for this activity?
6. What student motivational suggestions would you share with the next instructor?
7. At what point in the semester was this activity completed (i.e., second week, midterm, etc.)?
8. What needs to be repaired, replaced, or ordered before next time?

Form 4: Reflections After the Semester

1. Overall, what improvements would you suggest to make this a better course? Please provide details.
2. Which assignments should be modified and how?
3. Which assignments should be entirely replaced and why?
4. How might you reorganize the course, if at all?
5. Were students motivated to learn in this class (i.e., attendance, enthusiasm, etc.)? What recommendations for improvement would you make?
6. How effective were the teaching methods you used? What recommendations for improvement would you make?
7. List any people that helped you and how you contacted them.
8. If you have computer files related to the course, where can they be found?
9. Did you find any additional texts or references useful? Please provide details.
10. How can you be contacted the next time this course is taught?
11. When were your office hours? How well were they attended? What suggestions would you have for further improvement?

Useful websites and sources:

https://ciel.viu.ca/sites/default/files/getting_started_on_your_course_portfolio.pdf

<https://ciel.viu.ca/scholarly-teaching-practice/recognition-achievements-teaching-and-learning-program/course-portfolios>

<https://web.uri.edu/teach/files/Course-Portfolios.pdf>

Getting to know your students – Intercultural Understanding Inventory

The aim of this tool is to help in assessing students' diverse cultural background for intercultural understanding. You can use this tool in various ways to help you better understand your students which is a key in a teaching and learning process. The following sections will describe a possible solution to execute this tool as an assignment to your students.

Each student will create a Personal Cultural Inventory at the beginning of the course, using the tools below. They will work with others to compare themselves and talk about the implications of what they discover about their similarities and differences for themselves as international students. Over the semester, they will consider in which aspects they experience privilege, or in which they might consider themselves to be marginalized, which helps them to understand the source of differences between them and their peers' perspectives.

ASSIGNMENT: Who are you as a cultural being? As you prepare for this assignment, think about the cultures in which you participate according to the following categories:

- Ethnic background, first language
- Second or more languages
- Gender identity, Sexual orientation
- Ability status age
- Marital status, family,
- Socio-economic status or class
- Geographical background
- Educational background, Profession
- Religion
- Any other categories you can think of

In addition, use the following indicators to think about your cultural frames of reference. Where would you place yourself and your home culture(s) in the different areas? You don't need to cover every aspect, but do think about the things that stand out to you as you read through the list.

CONTINUUM OF CULTURAL VARIANTS - Compiled by Barbara Marler, Illinois Resource Center (2000)

FAMILY LIFE

- Temporary / permanent
- Extended / nuclear / linear
- Emotional closeness / distance
- Matriarchal / patriarchal

SOCIAL INTERACTIONS

- Use, value, and sharing of space
- Eye Contact

- Formal / Informal Behavior
- Symmetrical / Complimentary
- Degree of Demonstrativeness

EDUCATION

- Values and Curriculum
- Level of Prestige of teachers
- View and Value of Children
- Teaching and Learning Styles

WORK AND ACHIEVEMENT

- Competition / Cooperation
- Survival / Materialism / Self-Actualization
- Status of Occupations

INDIVIDUALITY

- Role definitions and flexibility
- Independence / Interdependence / Dependence
- Confrontation / Harmonization
- Rebellion / Conformity

WEALTH AND MATERIALISM

- Acquisition of tangibles and Intangibles
- Life Long Goals
- Evaluation of Lifetime achievements

TIME

- Level of Concern
- Past and Future Orientation
- Use present TIME (walks, runs, flies)
- Monochronic / Polychronic

AGE

- Views toward youth, middle age, and elderly
- Perceptions of Childhood and Adulthood
- Age of Majority
- Rites of Passage

SPACE

- Territoriality
- Generous / Restricted Use
- Use of Boundaries
- Social Interactions

COMMUNICATION AND LINGUISTICS

- Verbal / Nonverbal
- Tone / Pitch / Rhythm / Intonation
- Phonetic / Non-Phonetic

RELIGIOUS TENETS

- Monotheistic / Pantheistic / Polytheistic
- Spiritualistic / Humanistic
- Christianity / Hinduism / Buddhism / Confucianism / Taoism / Muslim / Etc.

NATURE

- Industrial / Agricultural
- Dominance Over / Harmonization with Nature
- Level of Science and technology Development
- National Parks
- Pollution Control

Source:

Commins, N. (2013). Personal Cultural Inventory. Notes of Multicultural Education course, University of Turku.

Planning your course – constructive alignment

The aim of this tool is to help you better plan your lecture or course by prompting you to think around basic curriculum design principles. In order to be able to provide an enhanced learning experience you need to know what you want to achieve with your course.

Constructive alignment (Biggs, 1999) provides you with a framework to think about the interconnectedness of learning outcomes, teaching and learning activities and assessment. It is your responsibility to create a supportive and challenging learning environment for all students and aligning these three elements help you do that. The following figure helps you with the necessary questions to think through when planning your lesson or course.

Source: Biggs, J. (2003): Aligning Teaching and Assessment to Curriculum Objectives. (Imaginative Curriculum Project, LTSN Generic Centre)

By teaching a course in which purpose, teaching, and assessment are aligned, a relationship of trust with students is created. When students are told what they should be able to demonstrate (learning outcomes), but are not assessed on these outcomes, they understandably feel confused and cheated. When teachers have clear learning outcomes, teach to and assess those outcomes, they may build a trusting relationship with their students.

Formulation of learning outcomes

We recommend starting at the end. Ask yourself the question: what do you want your students to know or be able to do at the end of the teaching and learning activity or at the end of the semester etc. Form the answer as statements that refer to a specific content/topic in a specific context and use action verbs to describe what you want your students to be able to do. Always think about assessment: how will you be able to assess whether your students reached the desirable level of outcome regarding each learning outcome or not.

In order to better scale learning outcomes we suggest using Bloom's taxonomy which is a classification of learning objectives for different complexity. Try to challenge yourself and

move beyond the level of “remember” and “understand” and provide your students with more complex and challenging learning outcomes. The following figure demonstrates the different levels of the taxonomy with possible tasks and action verbs that you can use when formulating your learning outcomes.

Bloom's Taxonomy

Don't forget, that learning outcomes, learning and teaching activities and assessment are interconnected. You can use Bloom's taxonomy to plan for activities and assessment methods as well!

The following figure gives you examples on how to construct learning outcomes.

Examples

Action Verb	Content/Topic	Context	Demonstrable Outcome
Construct	a reference list	using an appropriate disciplinary style	Construct a reference list using an appropriate disciplinary style
Demonstrate	effective negotiation skills	with health care providers	Justify solutions to case studies set in hospitals with an identified health care provider
Apply	principles of good learning & teaching	in higher education	Detail your approach to teaching, drawing on your own students' learning experiences
Sythesise	elements of a claim or defence	according to law	Prepare court documents in accordance with the relevant court rules and within the required timeframes

Adapted from Macquarie University (2015) FILT

The following template table will guide you through on how to communicate the alignment of course-level learning outcomes with assessment and teaching and learning activities. You can use this table to align your course-level learning outcomes with programme-level outcomes or you can check how your course would align to another course where you would like to teach in the context of teaching mobility.

<p>Course-Specific Learning Outcomes</p> <p>What will students know, value, and be able to do by the end of the course?</p> <p><i>Note: Courses typically have 5-8 learning outcomes.</i></p> <p>By the end of the course, successful students will be able to:</p>	<p>Assessment Methods</p> <p>What assessment methods will provide evidence that students have achieved the LO?</p> <p>How will feedback be given to students regarding their achievement of the LO?</p> <p>What assessment methods will need help to inform and improve student progress towards the LO?</p>	<p>Teaching & Learning Activities (TLA)</p> <p>What TLAs will students actively engage in as they progress towards this learning outcome?</p> <p>What TLAs will help to support students in their ability to achieve the LO?</p> <p><i>Note: These activities can occur both inside and outside the classroom.</i></p>	<p>Alignment with Program or Major Level Learning Outcomes</p> <p>What program-level or major-level learning outcomes does this course-level learning outcome align with?</p>
1.			
2.			
...			

Sources:

<https://centre.cc.umanitoba.ca/development/resources/course-alignment/>

<https://teaching.unsw.edu.au/learning-outcomes>

Teaching international students – innovative pedagogical methods

When on a teaching mobility (or even at your home university) you could encounter various teaching situations. Philip Warwick from the York Management School compiled the following list on what to consider when teaching international students which could be applied in multiple scenarios as well:

1. Preparation
2. Consider your assumptions
3. Manage expectations
4. Gentle pace introductions
5. Group work
6. Encourage speaking in class
7. Case studies
8. Assessment strategies
9. Get to know your students
10. Make time to reflect on how it went

The detailed list of suggestions can be read here: https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/assets.creode.advancehe-document-manager/documents/hea/private/10_tips_teaching_internat_sts_1568036909.pdf

Selecting specific teaching strategies and methods is a challenging task, but consider the logic that we presented in the previous tool with constructive alignment. The Teach with Erasmus+ project compiles tools for innovative pedagogical methods that you can use when you are on a teaching mobility. These innovative pedagogical methods can be used in your regular teaching as well, but for different professional reasons they are suited for enhancing the learning experience in a teaching mobility scenario.

The **Catalogue of pedagogical tools and methods** (descriptions, demonstrative videos, podcasts) are available on the project website: <https://teachwitherasmus.eu/resources/catalogue-pedagogical-tools-methods>

Therefore in this tool we are not going to deal with teaching strategies in detail but focus on other aspects of the teaching process.

Getting useful feedback from students – student evaluation of teaching

The explorative research that we conducted in the Teach with Erasmus+ project also highlighted the importance of useful feedback from students in enhancing the teaching mobility experience. Student voice is an important source of information regarding teaching quality although not without bias.

Literature on student evaluation of teaching often questions the validity and reliability of these tools for their lack of evidence regarding connections to teaching effectiveness and students learning (Clayson, 2018). Therefore we must exercise caution when interpreting these results, therefore we include it here, for academics' individual use and not for quality assessment of teaching mobility on the institutional level. Student evaluation of teaching can be a great source for self-reflection and professional development for academics (Chism et al, 2017).

We have created a simple tool that you can use to gather useful feedback from students. The tool contains three open-ended question where the students have to provide that usually “Along what dimensions you usually evaluate the quality of an academic course?”. With this method, students themselves provide meaningful and various dimensions to assess your course, instead of a prescribed list that may have different meaning for students. The next question ask students to rate these three elements on two dimensions. The first simply ask students to rate the course along the given dimensions on a scale of 1 to 7. The second instruct students to think about their best learning experience so far and compare this current course to their best experience on a 1 (this course was worse) to 7 (this course was better) on the same dimensions provided earlier. This way you have a general course evaluation and a relative course evaluation. The last question work as a Net Promoter Score (NPS) asking students that how likely given their current experiences that they would repeat the same learning experience (1-10). This would measure their intention of return and according to the NPS logic a percentage can be calculated by summarizing the percentage of students who gave points from 1 to 6 (they are detractors), from 7 to 8 (they are passives) and 9 or 10 (they are promoters) and subtracting the percentage of detractors from the percentage of promoters. A positive value in this scale indicates a higher return intent. At the end, you can add an open-ended question for students to provide additional comments to their evaluation.

You can use or customize the following template that builds on the logic previously described. You can execute it in a paper-based format or move the evaluation online (e.g. Qualtrics is suited to allow students to add their own dimensions for measurement).

Relative Course Evaluation Method

1) When you think about whether an academic course/lesson was good or bad, usually what are the dimensions that you consider?

- a) Please, write the dimensions in the appropriate part of the following table!
- b) Please, rate our current course/lesson according to these dimensions! (1 – bad; 7 – excellent)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. dimension:							
2. dimension:							
3. dimension:							

2) Now think about your best learning experience in Higher Education (any course/lesson in any university). Compare our current course/lesson to this best learning experience of yours! Use the same dimensions as before!

(1 – this course/lesson was much worse compared to my best experience; 4 – this course/lesson was more or less the same as my best experience; 7 – this course/lesson outperformed my best experience)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. dimension given by you in the previous question							
2. dimension given by you in the previous question							
3. dimension given by you in the previous question							

3) If you were to repeat this learning experience how likely that you would enrol in this course/lesson? (Disregarding the fact whether it is obligatory or not)

(1 – extremely unlikely; 10 – extremely likely)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

4) If you have any comments of constructive feedback regarding our course/lesson, you can write it here:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Sources:

Chism, N. V., Holley, M. & Harris, C. J. (2017). 9: Researching the impact of educational development. *To Improve the Academy*, 31, 129-145.

Clayson, D. E. (2018). Student evaluation of teaching and matters of reliability. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 4, 666-681.

